

STUDY OF PERFORMANCE OF INITIAL PUBLIC OFFERINGS (IPOS) AT NATIONAL STOCK EXCHANGE IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

With the implementation of liberalization and globalization policies, the Indian capital market had experienced a paradigm shift in its overall practices and initiatives. There were significant reforms both in the primary and secondary market. Presently, as per the SEBI guideline a corporate entity wants to raise capital from the primary market must go either through initial public offering (IPO), follow-on-public offer (FPO), rights issue, private placement or through euro issue.

Primary Market

□ IPO Process

The Indian capital market has emerged as one of the prominent demand driver for more participation of foreign institutional investors (FIIs) and domestic financial institutions (DFIs). Earlier the middle class investors have little option to put their hard earned money in productive investment avenues. They usually preferred the fixed deposit offered by banks or post office. The traditional investment instruments were hugely popular because they were safe, gave decent returns and were easy to invest in. But today, investors find that traditional instruments are more about wealth preservation than wealth creation, when they are better served by investment alternatives like mutual funds and IPOs.

Key Words: capital market, primary and secondary market, initial public offering (IPO), foreign institutional investors (FIIs), traditional instruments.

I. Introduction

An IPO is usually the first public offer of securities in the primary market by a company at its inception. The transition from being a private company to a public company is one of the most eventful occasions in the lifecycle of a corporate entity, and this transition is availed of by the corporate entities through IPO process.

Investors used to shy away from the market after burning their fingers in some of those premium issues which are, at present, being quoted much lesser than their issue price and even below their par value.

The first public issue in the annals of National Stock Exchange (NSE) which successfully follows the path of book building mechanism was Hughes Software Limited in the year 1999.

In India the first IPO driven boom was experienced during 1977-80, when the FERA (Foreign Exchange Regulation Act) regulated (presently it is replaced by FEMA [foreign exchange management act]) companies were asked to reduce their foreign holdings through public offers. Ponds, Hindustan Lever Limited (now Hindustan Unilever limited), Colgate and dozens of other companies were very much successful in attracting a large number of new investors to the capital market.

II Review Of Literature - Review of Literature done through following

Article by M. Mayur, Manoj Kumar in their titled “Determinants of Going-Public Decision in an Emerging Market- Evidence from India” on January-March, 2013 investigates the determinants of going-public decision of the Indian firms. The determinants were investigated by examining both ex-ante characteristics of the IPO firms and ex-post IPO consequences of the IPOs.

Fernando, A Rosary Ramona; Deo, Malabika; Zhagaiah, R in their research titled “Stock Price Performance of Initial Public Offerings: Evidence from India” published by International Journal of Research in Social Sciences on May, 2013 examines the price performance of Initial Public Offerings (IPOs) in India.

III. Objectives of the Study

1. To measure the performance of some selected issues through IPO in the short-run
2. To analyze the long-run performance of those issues as very little work has been done so far in Indian context
3. To ascertain the extent of under/over pricing of such issues
4. To make aware the common investors about the changing paradigm in equity investment & to give some basics of investing in primary market & IPO.

IV. Methodology

1. The methodology I have employed here for measuring price performance (both for short-run and long-run) is coined by Aggarwal, Leal and Hernandez (1993).
2. Using daily returns I have calculated the market adjusted abnormal return (MAAR) for each IPO on the 1st day of trading.

3. The other methodology to identify the short-run performance as well as the long run performance is the calculation of abnormal return (AR) and the cumulative abnormal return (CAR) using the event study methodology.

V. Performance of initial public offerings IPOs in National Stock Exchange

The Indian capital market has observed a strong increase in the number of foreign direct investment (FDI) projects in India. This shows that the global investors view the country as an attractive investment destination. In fact, India is ranked fourth most attractive destination in terms of FDI project and in terms of FDI value, it is the third best country in the world just behind China and Brazil.

1. The conceptual discourse of investment and security analysis and various relevant issues pertaining to IPO market should be properly understood.
2. The pattern and direction of the IPO market scenario in India have a positive impact on the effectiveness.
3. To explore the current trend and dimension of international scenario of IPO markets and its impact.

The rationality of the study can be viewed from three distinct but interrelated aspects viz. from the point of view of the (i) issuing companies, (ii) society, and (iii) the investors.

(i) From the point of view of issuing companies

The issuing companies“ desire to access the capital market, since going public raises cash and this fund can be utilised for various purposes. Particularly, it is seen that the reason for going public is to raise capital for modernization, expansion and diversification and too some extent to retire old debt and raise money for working capital requirement. So initial public offering is the safest bet for companies to raise capital but this involves some cost.

Other reasons for going public include increased visibility and reputation of the company, which is very essential in today’s market scenario, and enables the company to better valuation in future.

(ii) From the point of view of the society

India, however, needs heavy dose of investments to upgrade and develop infrastructure and also to achieve financial independence and full employment. The road is still very far. Moreover, channelising the small savings of the public through

IPOs to the sectors that are considered essential to the community is what required today for rapid industrialization. As such, ensuring maximum utilization of such scarce resources of the country is of paramount importance.

(iii) From the point of view of investors

With the diminishing returns of bank deposit and the continuous increase in the standard of living and what is even more visible is the increased aspiration of middle class Indians. Technically, investors provide risk capital to the business. They need regular updated and quality information to assess whether to buy, hold or sell their equity investment. Also, they are interested to know the ability of the business to survive, prosper and to pay dividends on a continuously increasing scale.

In fact, it has been noticed that the biggest dilemma facing the small investors is that they cannot judge the right entry and right exit time in the market. Poor quality and voluminous information as is provided in the prospectus of the public issue is often camouflaged through some elusive information which often mislead the common investors

During boom in the stock market it is the market operators and the speculators who used to reap the benefit of the situation, where the small investors fail to take any advantage out of it. In most of the cases they enter the market so late that the tidal waves of the market by then starts settling down and that time may be the ideal time to exit from the market.

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